

Preparation and Characterization of Naphthoxides of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V)

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Compounds of composition $MCl_n(ONp)_{3-n}$, where $M=Nb$ or Ta , ONp =anion of β -naphthol and $n=0$ to 4, have been prepared by digesting pentachlorides of the metals with β -naphthol in appropriate molar ratios in carbon tetrachloride. Their structures have been elucidated from elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility, infrared and TGA studies.

COMPARED to alkoxides, very little work has been carried out on the synthesis of metal phenoxides and naphthoxides, inspite of their utility as catalysts in many industries¹. Prasad and coworkers² isolated two series of compounds of anhydrous aluminium chloride with β -naphthol. Halides of titanium(IV) and zirconium(IV) are known to react with phenols and naphthols to form the corresponding derivatives but their structural information is lacking³. Reaction of selenium dithiocyanate with naphthols has been found to be useful for introducing SCN group into organic compounds⁴. Naphthols have been reported to be most effective and convenient amongst the phenols for the separation of ruthenium from uranium⁵. Naphthoxides of beryllium(II) and tungsten(V) have been isolated by reacting their halides with β -naphthol⁶. It is, therefore, of interest to isolate and characterise naphthoxides of transition metals. In the present communication, we report the preparation of naphthoxides of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) and propose a possible structure on the basis of elemental analysis, molar conductance, TGA, magnetic and infrared spectral studies.

Experimental

Naphthol (A.R.) was purified by crystallisation from dry benzene. Pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum, were Fluka, analytical grade, and were used without further purification. All the organic solvents were of AnalaR grade. They were further dried by appropriate drying agents and fractionally distilled.

Compounds of composition $MCl_4(ONp)$, $MCl_3(ONp)_2$ and $MCl_2(ONp)_3$, where M stands for niobium or tantalum and ONp stands for the anion of β -naphthol, were obtained by mixing corresponding pentachlorides with β -naphthol in exact 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 molar ratio in dry carbon tetrachloride and continuous stirring at room temperature till there was no evolution of HCl gas. But in case of compounds of composition $MCl(ONp)_4$ and $M(ONp)_5$, the corresponding

mixture solutions were heated occasionally (not more than 60°). To ensure complete substitution by naphthoxy groups in the last compound, β -naphthol in 1 : 5 molar ratio was taken in a little excess and digested till there was no evolution of HCl gas. The compounds so obtained were filtered, washed repeatedly with dry benzene and finally dried under vacuum.

Niobium and tantalum were estimated as their pentoxides and chlorine by Volhard's method. Infrared spectra of the complexes were recorded on a double grating infrared spectrophotometer, Perkin-Elmer 337 and 621, in KBr pellets. Molar conductance values of $10^{-8}M$ solutions of these compounds in nitrobenzene were determined using a cell of cell constant 0.384 at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ with a Toshniwal conductivity bridge, CLOI/01A Sr. No. 447. Thermogravimetric analysis was carried out on a Stanton thermogravimetric balance, model AD-2 at a heating rate of 5°/min. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on a Guoy's balance at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The reactions of pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum with β -naphthol in carbon tetrachloride were found to be slow but became facile on digestion. All attempts to isolate a solvate of β -naphthol with pentachlorides of niobium and tantalum at room temperature were unsuccessful, possibly because of the greater lability of the proton of naphthol. The niobium compounds gave dull orange crystals whereas the tantalum compounds were sulphur yellow in colour. Stoichiometric composition of these compounds was established by elemental analysis and results are reported in Table 1. All these compounds are moisture sensitive and change their colour on exposure but are sufficiently stable in dry air. They are insoluble in most organic solvents except slight solubility in nitrobenzene and dimethylformamide. Molar conductance values of $10^{-8}M$ solutions in nitrobenzene (Table 1) suggest that the compounds are non-ionic

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE ISOLATED NIOBIUM AND TANTALUM COMPLEXES

Compound	Colour	Elemental analysis				Molar conductance in nitrobenzene (ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹)
		% Found		% Req'd.		
		M	Cl	M	Cl	
Nb(ONp) ₅	Brick red	10.80	—	11.50	—	13*
NbCl(ONp) ₄	Light brick red	13.00	4.95	13.32	5.07	2
NbCl ₂ (ONp) ₃	Deep orange	14.28	11.25	15.70	12.00	3
NbCl ₃ (ONp) ₂	Orange	18.38	21.28	19.15	21.97	2
NbCl ₄ (ONp)	Orange	25.02	36.82	24.16	37.05	16*
Ta(ONp) ₅	Dull yellow	20.00	—	20.20	—	10*
TaCl(ONp) ₄	Deep yellow	21.82	4.08	22.90	4.50	2
TaCl ₂ (ONp) ₃	Sulphur yellow	25.89	9.72	26.60	10.40	2
TaCl ₃ (ONp) ₂	Yellow	30.74	17.81	31.20	18.60	11*
TaCl ₄ (ONp)	Yellow	37.25	29.31	38.80	30.40	2

* In dimethylformamide.

in nature. Molecular weight determinations could not be carried out because the compounds are insoluble in solvents suitable for cryoscopy. They are diamagnetic, excluding thereby the possibility of any reduction of the metal to the lower oxidation state.

Infrared spectra of these compounds show a significant change in the spectrum of the pure ligand on complex formation. The broad band in the region 3360-3460 cm⁻¹, assigned to hydrogen bonded phenolic hydroxyl group in β -naphthol⁷, is altogether missing in all the compounds. This indicates that there is no phenolic hydroxyl group present in these compounds, which is also supported by the observation that hydrogen chloride gas was liberated during the course of their preparation. A perusal of the spectra of these compounds suggests that the changes in various bands are similar to the ones observed for various aromatic tertiary bases upon complex formation with metal⁷ and non-metal halides⁸. The sharp bands at 3052 and 3074 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν (C-H) in β -naphthol are observed at the same positions in the compounds. Furthermore, the most important and strong band at 1260 cm⁻¹ in pure β -naphthol⁹ due to ν (C-O) stretching mode, shifts to lower spectral regions by about 40-50 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of these compounds. This shift may be attributed to the drainage of electrons from the ring to the metal through C-O bond. The important bands are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PRINCIPAL INFRA RED BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE NIOBIUM(V) AND TANTALUM(V) COMPLEXES

Compound	ν (O-H)	ν (O-C)	ν (M-O)	ν (M-Cl)
NpOH	3400	1260	—	—
Nb(ONp) ₅	—	1190	540, 580	—
NbCl(ONp) ₄	—	1220	546, 578	349
NbCl ₂ (ONp) ₃	—	1210	548, 570	352
NbCl ₃ (ONp) ₂	—	1198	542, 568	348
NbCl ₄ (ONp)	—	1204	540	340
Ta(ONp) ₅	—	1210	502, 545	—
TaCl(ONp) ₄	—	1215	518, 548	333
TaCl ₂ (ONp) ₃	—	1198	510, 550	342
TaCl ₃ (ONp) ₂	—	1220	498, 552	338
TaCl ₄ (ONp)	—	1202	506	335

Metal coordination to the ligand has been further confirmed by the appearance of new bands (not present in the pure ligand) in the lower wave number region. Intense bands around 570-580 cm⁻¹ in case of niobium and around 540-550 cm⁻¹ in case of tantalum compounds may be assigned to ir active terminal ν (M-O) stretching modes. Such type of bands, assigned to terminal M-O bonds in the alkoxides of these metals, have also been reported earlier in the same region^{10,11}. It is interesting to note that in these compounds no band around 900-930 cm⁻¹, which could be assigned to Nb=O or Ta=O stretching modes¹², has been observed suggesting that no oxygen abstraction occurs in these compounds.

In the case of the compound of composition NbCl₄(ONp), an intense and sharp band at 540 cm⁻¹ has also been observed. Since this band is well below the range 570-580 cm⁻¹ observed for terminal ν (Nb-O) stretching mode¹¹, it may be

attributed to bridging Nb Nb mode. This assignment is quite in agreement with earlier observations^{11,13}. Furthermore, a sharp intense band at 340 cm⁻¹ assigned to ν (Nb-Cl) stretching vibrations is observed which is in agreement with the assignments of Djordjevic¹⁴ and with the reported ν (Nb-Cl) vibrations for octahedral complexes¹⁵. No band that could be assigned to bridging chlorine, which is expected to fall below 330 cm⁻¹¹⁵, has been observed. Based upon ir spectral data and insolubility in various solvents, a possible dimeric structure via bridging through naphthoxy groups may be proposed. Similar observations have been made in case of tantalum compounds. These propositions also find support from previous work on the alkoxides and phenoxides of niobium and tantalum¹⁶⁻¹⁸.

Thermal mode of decomposition and relative strength of bonds in these naphthoxides have been inferred from the weight changes noted from thermograms. In the case of the compound NbCl₄(ONp), a molecule of chloronaphthalene is lost at ~158° leaving behind niobium oxytrichloride, which decomposes further via dioxymonochloride (NbO₂Cl) formation at ~260° followed by

subsequent disproportionation to the pentoxide and pentachloride¹⁹ at about 600°. However, in case of fully substituted naphthoxide, i.e. Nb(ONp)₅, the major intermediate products are dinaphthyl ether and niobiumoxytrinaphthoxides as shown below :

The final product in all the naphthoxides has been found to be M₂O₅. Formation of these intermediates is supported by the earlier reports on the mode of decompositions of alkali metal²⁰ and transition metal phenoxides²¹. It can thus be concluded that these naphthoxides have sufficient thermal stability because of their polymeric structure.

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